

Language Is Leaving Me:

Epigenetic memory in multilingual visual and verbal AI

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ABSTRACT

In 2021 Open AI released CLIP and VQGAN, neural network architectures for still and nascent moving text-to-image models. The response was overwhelming though in the rush to implementation issues surrounding data sources, algorithmic parameters and prompt engineering were deemphasized. *Language Is Leaving Me – An AI Cinematic Opera Of The Skin*, a mixed reality performance installations focuses on AI, algorithmic rendering, sound, and biometrics through the lens of epigenetic, or inherited traumatic memories of cultures of diaspora. Examining multi-lingual multi-visual renderings of prompt engineering combined with Stable Diffusion image-to-image comparisons it reveals inherent structural flaws and biases highlighting challenges for emerging visual taxonomy's representation of non-quantifiable human experiences across cross-cultural dimensions.

CCS CONCEPTS

- Computing methodologies~Human Computer graphics~Image manipulation~Image-based rendering
- Computing methodologies~Computer graphics~Animation~Motion Processing
- Theory of computation~Semantics and reasoning~Program semantics~Categorical semantic

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, algorithmic bias, epigenetics, diaspora, performance, multi language prompt engineering

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1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLM) are built on neural networks transformer models that learn pattern recognition to comprehend predictive models of sequential data [1]. These models have decreased their use of tagging systems for textual

models, but this is not how current AI systems work with AI images, as the derived information is too complex. Even anonymized data can be manipulated into reproducing parts of that training data previously removed [2]. Open AI has suggested it is close to impossible to prevent open source models from causing harm as input classifiers can amplify bias, a well know flaw embedded in training models. When applied to proprietary systems like Google's controversial Gemini (previously called Bard)[3], this problem of unsafe AI generation is one of the most irrefutable problems in the field and an ongoing issue.

Epigenetics is rDNA chromosome modification that are not part of an organism's original DNA structure [4]. It has been scientifically validated that epigenetic trauma exists in worms throughout many generations but not yet definitively in humans [5]. However, psychologists are already incorporating ways that trauma can be intergenerationally manifested, examined, and healed [6]. As an artist and researcher my practice focuses on investigating newly emerging AI cinema and its derived synthetic media powered by LLMs. I wondered how AI models, specifically newly emerging AI visual models dealt with the unspoken, the non-quantifiable, and psychological nuances their newly developing rendered outputs, including epigenetic trauma. To do this I created "Language Is Leaving Me – an AI cinematic Opera Of The Skin" (LLM), a biometric performed AI cinema installation partially powered by human EMG (electromyography) measurements, meaning the facial muscles of a volunteer audience member. The EMG patches were placed on the volunteer's face to generate sections of the live time sonic environment, meaning their smile (positive) or frown (negative) changed the music. The film used texts translated through Google Translate from the original English language into Yiddish, Chinese, Tamil, and Xhosa. These arrays of text prompts revealed devastating aspects of these multilingual algorithmic rendering processes. It showed how LLMs can alter and erase the visual, semiotic, and signified memory and identity of populations of diaspora, obliterating cultural and personal visual and verbal history. The resulting videos produce a visual cognitive AI based aphasia, meaning multilingual visual AI had limited to no ability to render my epigenetic psychological interiority throughout different cultural contexts. I found this aphasic deficit full of possibilities for artistic practice.

2 A Brief Overview of Rapid Developments

VQGAN (Vector Quantized Generative Adversarial Network) and CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training) transformer and generative technologies produce text-to-image conversions and were first published by Katherine Crowson using the Python software programming language [7]. CLIP decides which tagged captions VQGAN, aligns best with so it can be assigned to a specific image generation. The CLIP model includes its own separate transformer architecture as smart indexing but does not generate anything itself so it can be used with other convolutional neural network image architectures. It deals with unseen datasets, referred to as zero-shot learning, meaning the model can observe samples from information classes that were not included in the original training model [8]. CLIP is open source, whereas other robust visual classification models like DALL-E, a diffusion model that uses a different set of transformers and also developed by OpenAI were not [9]. CLIP arose from investigations into zero-shot transfer, natural language supervision, and multimodal learning. VQGAN arose from previous text-to-image transfer models like AttnGAN (Attention GAN), [10] [11] [12] [13] [14]. Crowson refers to CLIP as the “Perceptor” (or selector) and VQGAN as the “Generator” meaning the generator of images. This means there are not smart discriminators for filtering information outside of common contemporary data harvesting techniques. The easiest way for artists to work with VQGAN and CLIP in early 2021 was to use Google Colab notebooks, as they allowed a download of either partial or entire databanks [15].

3 One Word Many Results

The Google Colab notebook “VQGAN+CLIP (with pooling).ipynb” was used for initial tests in 2021, even though these models have subsequently attracted widespread criticism [16] [17][18] [19]. This notebook was chosen because in 2021 not much was available for artists to use for experimentation. The English word “queer” was selected as an initial text prompt because of its British English vernacular meaning of different or strange, and the more recent gendered use. The datasets Faceshq_5; ImageNet_10245; ImageNet_16394; OpenImages_8192_5; WikiArt_1024; and WikiArt_16384 were used and every dataset returned strikingly similar images, though millions of different images were supposedly used. The word “boy” and “girl” were added in English and returned disturbing results. Because I was working with Chinese and Indian software developers, we decided to use Google Translate with both a literal and slang or colloquial vernacular translation of the term “queer”, “queer boy” and “queer girl” of Chinese, Hindi, and Tamil terms. It should be noted that The Google Colab version referenced above initially included a translate option, but it was subsequently removed without notice.

Figure1: Similarity of six different image banks for the word “queer”

The standard Chinese language image for queer boy returned alcoholic drinks, ambiguous and nonsensical Chinese characters and a rainbow flag off to the side. The slang translation of queer boy returned a male face with the eyebrow morphing into possible eyeglasses or an eyebrow with pinkish skin tone, a nude amorphous body, and indecipherable Chinese characters. The same variables were run for Chinese queer girl. They returned bottles of alcohol, pink colors, and a fleshy colored background with a figure with long hair. The slang variation returned a possible rainbow flag, a sexualized rear torso view of luscious pink flesh, and incomprehensible Chinese characters.

Figure 2: Chinese from google Translate and from native speakers (slang) – “queer boy” and “queer girl”

The Hindi and Tamil fluent programmer used the COCO image bank. Hindi queer returned pseudo-Hindi script, a wheat-colored and multi-colored object, and a splotchy green background. Queer in the Tamil language resembled a landscape with a pink river against a pale blue background without any representation of a human being. The Hindi queer boy looked like a topographical map with pseudo-Hindi characters and the Tamil queer boy had pink sections, and a dark brown undistinguishable object. Queer girl in Hindi resembled an orange, white, and green flag, and landscape with indecipherable script. Queer girl in Tamil resembled an old sandstone temple with a blue sky and grotesque reddish-brown faces.

But What About Hindi and Tamil?

Queer - Hindi Native Speaker
Coco_42

Queer - Tamil Native Speaker
Coco_42

Figure 3: Queer in Hindi and Tamil, native speaker

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But What About Hindi and Tamil?

Queer Boy Hindi Native Speaker -
Coco Seed 42

Queer Boy Tamil Native Speaker -
Coco Seed 42

Queer Girl Hindi Native Speaker -
Coco Seed 42

Queer Girl Tamil Native Speaker -
Coco Seed 42

Figure 4: Queer boy and queer girl, Hindi, and Tamil native speaker

4 Making The Movie

I tried making moving images in Google Colab, but the results were not feasible. Briefly returning to traditional cinema, I made a short video “Language Is Leaving Me” with both original and copyright free archival footage. LILM explored a story about my epigenetic trauma as an agnostic Jew whose ancestors fled to the United States from the Eastern European Pale of Settlement in 1906. Right after I made the video the text-to-image model Stable Diffusion was released by Stability.ai [20]. It uses over five billion images from the LAION-5B image bank [21], a foundational dataset based on the diffusion model called Latent Diffusion [22].

On August 22, 2022 Stable Diffusion Web UI, also known as Automatic 1111, referring to the user’s Github name was released [23]. It allowed image-to-image comparisons and

offered more options than Google Colab. This was a huge breakthrough in attempting to develop AI cinema, with a DIY (Do It Yourself) approach. Throughout 2022 and into 2023 I processed my original five-minute video in Automatic1111 dividing it into 57 scenes. Each scene contained individual .png files created using a Split-To-Frames convertor, typically rendering 50-200 .pngs per scene, akin to the individual images in a flip book. The .pngs were batch processed through Automatic 1111’s image-to-image comparison and were given four sets of text prompts translated from my English language video into four different “librettos” in Chinese, Yiddish, Tamil, and Xhosa using Google Translate. This meant I wound up with 285 folders containing multilingual image-to-image .pngs text prompted in five languages.

English Original

The head of the residency, my friend and I all had coffee.

Yiddish

דער טפּ פּון דער רעזידענץ, און מיין פּריינד האבן געטראנק קאפּע.

Mandarin

驻地负责人、我和我的朋友都喝了咖啡。

Tamil

ரெசிடென்சி தலைவர், என் நண்பர் மற்றும் நான் அனைவரும் காபி சாப்பிட்டோம்.

Xhosa

Intloko yendawo yokuhlala, mna nomhlobo wam sasinekofu.

Each set of the 285 .png folders were reassembled into a MP4 video through the use of an FFMPEG script deployed in Terminal. The original FFMPEG conversion frames per second in the .MP4 contained highly disruptive flickering, a common problem during 2022 and 2023 in AI visual multi scene rendering. The AI interpolation needed to be slowed down for the human eye to comprehend it. After many attempts I located a usable flicker rate of approximately 20 fps, a different flow rate than traditional movies that are typically 25 or 30 fps.

```
ffmpeg -r 7 -start_number `ls | grep -E '[0-9]+\.[jpg$]' | sed 's/\.[jpg$]//' | sort -n | head -n 1` -i %05d.jpg resulting_video.mp4
```

Without the unlimited resources of OpenAI or using pay per use services like RunwayML, I built an expanded animation platform, as well as comparing and contrasting the multilingual flaws of both text-to-image and image-to-image uses of LLMs image data banks. I wanted to see how other datasets would interpret my epigenetic trauma, and they seemed to have obliterated it.

During 2023 I also created a biometric sound environment for the live performance installation LILM, which premiered at the Copernicus Science Center in Warsaw, Poland on October 7, 2023. This included a customized motherboard built from scratch in Shenzhen, China that received EMG input from the facial muscles of an audience volunteer and used Touch Designer to turn the signals into sound. It registered a frown (negative) or a

smile (positive) roughly corresponding to the general reactions of the viewing audience. This integration of the human animal into the film installation produced a modulated sonic environment created alongside the audience, as the volunteer viewer shared both their shared horror and fascination live time.

Figure 5: Volunteer audience member with EMG sensors on her face – red for frown, green for smile

Figure 6: Top left clockwise- English – “I could not image what she wanted to give me”, Chinese - 我无法想象她要给我什么 - Yiddish - איך האב זיך נישט געקענט פארשטעלן וואס זי וויל מיר גען , Xhosa - Andizange ndiyicinge into awayefuna ukundinika yona .

5 Making The Movie

My first test in 2021 in Google Colab using VQ Gan and CLIP to interpret the word queer revealed outrageous gaps and misrepresentations. The six datasets should have rendered multiple visual perspectives with these prompts, but they did

not. It seemed one standardized algorithmic transformer was interpreting a very nuanced human representation. This may be common knowledge for ChatGPT prompts, but for multilingual image-to-image prompts it is an emerging area. The second experiment with the words queer girl and queer boy did not use as many trials but the results were still completely flawed. The Chinese, Hindi, and Tamil scripts revealed cultural biases, incomplete or non-existent data and linguistic tagging and weighting of images that made absolutely no sense.

In 2022 I ran .png files of my short video through the Stable Diffusion LAION-5B dataset using the newly introduced image-to-image capabilities of Automatic 1111, a web-based user interface. This allowed an expanded animation representation to be created, something Google Colab could not successfully accomplish. The English text prompt used Google Translate to turn the films narration into Chinese, Yiddish, Tamil, and Xhosa using their original cursive scripts. I wanted to see how AI could render my subconscious memories and dreams of psychological, cultural, and spiritual trauma into another language’s visual image bank’s interpretation. The result showed ghastly and devastating cultural deformations. This is because LAION-5B is reliant on Web Crawl, which accesses three billion websites using popular shopping, corporate and general public upload sites to scrape its information. The main models and Web Crawl’s assessments are configured in English, Russian, French, and German [24]. The complexities behind the decisions populating the LAION 5-B dataset are beyond the scope of this paper.

Meaning using algorithmic smoothing and machine learning creates semantic taxonomies containing seismic fault lines in terms of interpreting algorithms into images. This is referred to as the “epistemics of training sets” or the fraught and complex relation between images and the concepts that tie those images to their linguistic meaning and that meaning to the semantic image tagging prompts deployed by algorithms [25]. This can also be thought of as “catastrophic forgetting”. Currently image tagging consists mostly of nouns, with verbs and adjectives thrown in to enhance their meaning. Epistemic AI attempts to create new mathematical models for decision making. Its operating premise is instead of inferring predictive models about data it has at its disposal, it will assume it has a paucity of data from which to make any sort of conclusion. Only since 2016 has the issue of epistemic uncertainty in machine language become an area of focus. It acknowledges the difficulty of comprehending in domain and out of domain sampling that causes model cognition to be insufficient. Another factor is the mundane human labor of image tagging by individuals whose first language is not English, and who lack the understanding and cultural nuance to comprehend what they are looking at. Paid by the word, it is advantageous for them to perform a cursory analysis of an image, tag it and move onto the next task at hand [26] [27] [28].

6 Thinking About The Future

Text-to-image transformer technologies VQGAN, CLIP, and various diffusion models such as Dall-e and Stable Diffusion are powerful additions in building AI based visual technologies. These technologies will be incorporated into many areas of contemporary life, from medical diagnosis to immigration, employment, education, credit and banking, security access, logistics, jurisprudence, advertising, the art world, NFTs, game development, the metaverse and many more. What these simple investigations glaringly demonstrate is how inaccurate and clumsy algorithmic process are when given open-ended multi-nuanced text prompts for visual information. Using my own epigenetic memories as an individual with over 1000 years of a culture of diaspora, I wanted to see how visual and multi-lingual AI would interpret my truth. What I found is that when terms are linguistically misaligned with cultural norms or underrepresented linguistic and cultural image datasets, inaccuracies multiply. Deeply problematic is what their final rendered output actually looks like. For the first experiment in 2021 using different image banks Faceshq_5, Imagenet_10245, ImageNet_16384, OpenImages8192_5, WikiArt_1024, and wikiArt_16384 and COCO combined with English, Chinese and Tamil revealed serious issues of bias and relevance. This most likely was the reason the translate option from this specifically referenced Google Colab notebook I used vanished. In 2023 when I ran image-to-image comparisons in LAION-5B through the Chinese, Yiddish, Tamil, and Xhosa language scripts the conceptual and semantic basis of the text prompt was obliterated. Semantic meaning was de-coupled from its visual referent.

As AI and especially visual AI moves forward there is an implicit but unstated assumption that whatever cannot be taxonomized and tagged will be rendered irrelevant or just cease to exist. This includes any culture, person, organization, or entity not aware of, capable of, or interested in, or having the resources to digitize both individual and collective visual memories and histories. Data not scrapped from contemporary easily accessible sources that are from the four or five most privileged languages will most likely be excluded, marginalized, misunderstood, and misrepresented if it manages to be represented at all. Chinese researchers, understanding the inherent limitations of these models are designing their own systems [29]. Since there are approximately 7000 languages in the world this is a problem multiplying exponentially when applied to linguistic models that are not notated and codified. Extrapolating to include styles of visual codification based on that linguistic tagging raises the likelihood for misunderstandings, misidentifications, exclusions, and obliteration for peoples of marginalized cultures. Facebook/Meta is attempting to tackle this problem with their “No Language Left Behind” project stating, “What does it take to double the language coverage of most existing translation models while ensuring high quality and safe translations?” [30] (Costa-jussà et. al. 2022). It is dubious, given the ethical and financial implications of Meta’s business models that their approach will be enough to solve the issue as their model ultimately boils down to a fiscal model, not one for the benefit of the common good. What about indigenous cultures that have

little or no representation? How will Meta deal with these issues?

This problem or deficit is so serious it is something world organizations like UNESCO are paying close attention to. They state that AI contains, “potential negative implications for the diversity and pluralism of languages, media, cultural expressions, participation, and equality” (UNESCO, n.d.). This means the responsibility falls squarely on the artists, coders, and others to reveal and reconfigure these glaring misrepresentations. I hope that my investigations, DIY methodology, and performance/installation piece can contribute to the ongoing dialogue.

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